

TECHNOLOGY-ENHANCED MATERIALS DEVELOPMENT FOR PROMOTING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE THROUGH “UNLIMITED POWER” BOOK: A FLIPPED CLASSROOM APPROACH

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Abstract: This article presents the design and rationale of a technology-enhanced teaching material based on Anthony Robbins' book *Unlimited Power* for upper secondary English language learners. The material is grounded in six principles of language acquisition, including authenticity, affective and cognitive engagement, positive attitude development, utilization of mental resources, language awareness, and communicative opportunities. Designed for B1+/B2 learners aged 15–16, the lesson adopts a Flipped Classroom approach and integrates digital tools such as Actively Learn, Ideaboardz, Hypothes.is, Wakelet, Edpuzzle, and Write & Improve. The activities promote the development of integrated language skills through collaborative learning, critical thinking, reflective writing, and project-based tasks. By engaging with authentic content and meaningful communication, learners enhance their communicative competence, digital literacy, creativity, and autonomous learning skills. The material also encourages personal growth and motivation through exposure to inspiring real-life stories and self-development concepts, creating a learner-centered and technology-rich educational environment.

Keywords: Materials Development, Communicative Competence, Flipped Classroom, Technology-Enhanced Learning, Authentic Materials, Language Acquisition, Digital Literacy, English Language Teaching, Collaborative Learning, Anthony Robbins.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada ingliz tilini o'rganuvchi yuqori sinf o'quvchilari uchun Entoni Robbinsning “Unlimited Power” kitobi asosida ishlab chiqilgan raqamli o'quv materiali va uning metodik asoslari yoritilgan. Material tilni o'zlashtirishning oltita muhim tamoyiliga tayangan holda yaratilgan bo'lib, ular autentiklik, affektiv va kognitiv faollik, ijobiy munosabatni shakllantirish, aqliy resurslardan foydalanish, til hodisalarini anglash hamda muloqot imkoniyatlarini kengaytirishni o'z ichiga oladi. Dars B1+/B2 darajadagi 15–16 yoshli o'quvchilar uchun mo'ljallangan bo'lib, teskari sinf (Flipped Classroom) modeli asosida Actively Learn, Ideaboardz, Hypothes.is, Wakelet, Edpuzzle va Write & Improve kabi raqamli platformalar yordamida tashkil etiladi. Taklif etilgan faoliyatlar o'quvchilarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasi, tanqidiy fikrlashi, raqamli savodxonligi, mustaqil ta'lim olish ko'nikmalari va hamkorlikda ishlash malakalarini rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi. Shuningdek, mazkur material o'quvchilarning shaxsiy rivojlanishi va o'qishga bo'lgan motivatsiyasini oshirishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'quv materiallarini ishlab chiqish, kommunikativ kompetensiya, teskari sinf modeli, raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalari, autentik materiallar, tilni o'zlashtirish, raqamli savodxonlik, ingliz tilini o'qitish, hamkorlikda o'qitish, Entoni Robbins.

Introduction

As Low (1989) mentioned: *“Designing appropriate materials is not a science: it is a strange mixture of imagination, insight and analytical reasoning”*.

The materials should be created by utilizing deeply researched learning and teaching principles.

For this reason, there were selected outlined below six specific teaching principles in developing all three teaching materials:

- Principle of Language Acquisition 1: Comprehensible and meaningful input/Authenticity
- Principle of Language Acquisition 2: Affective and cognitive engagement
- Principle of Language Acquisition 3: Encouraging positive attitude
- Principle of Language Acquisition 4: Utilizing mental resources
- Principle of Language Acquisition 5: Noticing specific language features
- Principle of Language Acquisition 6: Opportunities for enhancing communicative abilities

Tomlinson (2003) stated that needs of the learners should be put as the ultimate principle in creating teaching materials. Hence the needs of the students were the basement in creating these three teaching materials.

The ultimate purpose of all developed set of materials is ameliorating communicative abilities of the learners in meaningful way. However, other language skills are also integrated since four language skills are interconnected with each other. Thus, they can be considered as communicative activities in which created lots of opportunities for the learners to practice real language.

Main body

Teaching material

Technology based

Unlimited Power

Time: 75-80 minutes

Numeracy: 12

Grade: 9

Age: 15-16 years old

Level: B1+/B2

Integrated skills: speaking, writing, reading, listening

Objectives:

- SWBAT summarize the main points
- SWBAT give constructive feedback to their peers
- SWBAT analyze and annotate the text in online form
- SWBAT work collaboratively and create digital portfolios for their research project

Approach: Flipped Classroom Model

“Unlimited Power” by Anthony Robbins is uploaded in reading platform Actively Learn <http://www.activelylearn.com/> and they read the book in this platform. Learners should finalize reading whole book outside the class before doing the “Unlimited Power” activity in class.

Unlimited Power

Topic: Anthony Robbins “Unlimited Power” book

Warm-up [Lead-in]: 15-17 minutes

Students work individually and log in <https://ideaboardz.com/>. They are inspired to create virtual board about the content of the book by highlighting key points and essential parts.

In the next step, learners share the link of their board and invite others to discuss the main points & leave comments/recommendations.

Pre-stage [Collaborative annotation activity]: 18- 20 minutes

Students select any chapter from the book and create “flash mob annotation” in web 2 tool “Hypothes. is” <https://web.hypothes.is/>. Students are encouraged to think critically and analyze/discuss the chosen chapter

While-stage [Creating research project]: 30-35 minutes

Learners are divided into four equal groups and encouraged to work collaboratively and create research project about the book and its author in web 2 tool “Wakelet” <http://wakelet.com/>.

They share their work on any social web site that is available (Facebook, Flipgrid, Google Classrooms, Instagram, Telegram and etc.). Students review each other’s work and leave comments. In the end, each group presents orally their digital portfolio.

Post- stage: 15 -18 minutes

Students select one quotation/saying from the book and utilize it as a title for their essay. They are inspired to think critically and reflect on this quote by giving solid facts from the book. Trainees write their essay in “Write & Improve” platform <https://writeandimprove.com/>.

Back-up (Free activity): 25-30 minutes

Learners work individually and create mini-discussion lesson in digital tool “Edpuzzle” <https://edpuzzle.com/>. They are provided with the link of the video “10 BEST IDEAS | Unlimited Power | Tony Robbins | Book Summary” by Clark Kegley.

Link of the video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sVs-hmUFec0>

Learners should create open-ended & multiple- choice questions around the video. Then they work in pairs and share the link of their mini-lesson to each other. In the next step, each learner submit the created assignment of their partner.

Conclusion

Rationale: This teaching material is developed by utilizing the outlined below teaching principles:

- Principle of Language Acquisition 1: Comprehensible and meaningful input/Authenticity
- Principle of Language Acquisition 2: Affective and cognitive engagement
- Principle of Language Acquisition 3: Encouraging positive attitude
- Principle of Language Acquisition 4: Utilizing mental resources
- Principle of Language Acquisition 5: Noticing specific language features
- Principle of Language Acquisition 6: Opportunities for enhancing communicative abilities

This activity is specifically designed to check and ameliorate the comprehension of the learners about the book. They are encouraged to accomplish disparate tasks in which they might enhance their creativity, analytical skills, problem-solving skills, autonomous skills, teamwork and communicative abilities.

The book “Unlimited Power” by outstanding coach and writer on personal development Anthony Robbins is selected specifically for the benefits of the students, First and foremost, the book demonstrates authenticity in learning process. Reading the

books can bring many benefits and meaningful learning for the students. There are created sufficient opportunities for the learners to enhance vocabulary case, communicative abilities, pronunciation and acquiring the language in context. Additionally, they can alter their mindset, strengthen the memory and ameliorate their soft skills as well. As Tomlinson (2008) stated authenticity helps learners to utilize the language efficiently since they are immersed in experiential learning process.

The book consists of the life stories of people who achieved their dreams despite any challenges. This stimulates learners to think and connect with their personal life.

All the designed activities foster affective and cognitive engagement of the students. Cognitive and affective engagement might accelerate motivation and generate positive feelings such as happiness, enjoyment and empathy (McGrath, 2002). The content of the book is very interesting and students can apply knowledge of the book in real life. All the designed tasks stimulate learners to work independently and create disparate projects with the help of digital tools. Interesting tasks might foster communicative competence of the students (Tomlinson, 2003).

Utilizing mental resources such as personal evaluations and interpretations, predicting can ameliorate second language acquisition process (Tomlinson, 2008). Thus, there are designed tasks such as collaborative annotation activity and writing activity in which they should utilize their mental resources.

Language awareness of the students can be fostered if they are actively engaged in noticing particular features of the language (Arnold, 1999). Students are stimulated to back to the chapters of the book over and over again in order to do tasks. They summarize the key points, write a reflective writing on the quote and annotate the chapter by analyzing it. These aforementioned tasks lead learners to notice salient features of the language in natural way.

Students ought to have sufficient opportunities to produce the language and enhance their communicative skills (McGrath, 2002). All the tasks are specifically designed to create communicative atmosphere in which learners can increase their collaborative/communicative abilities by practicing the language actively.

This teaching material can have great impact on student learning for several reasons. Firstly, learners can acquire valuable life knowledge from the book. Secondly, they ameliorate 21st century digital skills and soft skills. Thirdly, they gain confidence and strong self-esteem. Fourthly, trainees acquire the language in meaningful way. Finally, students' communicative competence will be altered.

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